

Pokkali had significantly higher shoot dry weight and K:Na ratio under saline conditions than IR28 and IR20. In general, the highest salinity level resulted

in much lower shoot dry weights and K:Na ratios. Semitolerant variety IR20 responded best to ABA. □

Effect of salinity and abscisic acid (ABA) application on shoot dry weight and K:Na ratio of 3 rice varieties.

Treatment	Shoot dry weight (mg/plant)				K:Na ratio (shoot)			
	IR28	IR20	Pokkali	Mean	IR28	IR20	Pokkali	Mean
Control ^a	855	912	1095	—	176.1	187.5	125.0	—
Without ABA	409	395	774	526	10.69	8.44	14.21	11.11
With ABA	526	565	764	618	12.39	12.37	14.48	13.08
Mean	468	480	769		11.54	10.41	14.35	
LSD (0.05)								
Variety				81.2				1.10
ABA				66.3				0.90
Variety × ABA				114.8				1.55
Salinity level (dS/m)								
EC10				642				15.27
EC15				502				8.92
LSD (0.05)				66.3				0.90

^aControl values were not included in analysis of variance.

Integrated germplasm improvement – irrigated

MDU4, a high-yielding, cold-tolerant rice for Tamil Nadu

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Screening for cold tolerance in rice in the high area of Cumbum valley in Madurai district of Tamil Nadu, India (nocturnal temperature 12-14 °C Nov-Feb, during the rice crop flowering phase), identified the high-yielding, cold-tolerant line ACM16 (AC2836/Jagannath). It has been named MDU4 and released for planting in cooler regions of Tamil Nadu.

MDU4 is semidwarf, high tillering, and nonlodging. Average yield in adaptive trials was 5.9 t/ha, 17.3% higher than that of IR20 (Table 1). Maximum yield potential is 10.5 t/ha. It matures in 125-130 d.

MDU4 is highly tolerant of low temperature and has lower spikelet sterility than IR20 and MDU2 (Table 2). In addition, it exhibits little grain discoloration, which is a problem in IR20 and

Table 1. Yield of MDU4 (ACM16) in adaptive field trials, Tamil Nadu, India.

Trial site	Yield (t/ha)		
	ACM16 (MDU4)	MDU2	IR20
Madurai district	6.4	6.1	5.7
Dharmapuri	6.4	5.9	5.7
Salem	8.2	7.9	6.4
Overall mean	7.0	6.3	6.1
State seed farms (Keelagudalur Cumbum Valley)	5.4	4.3	4.4
National trials	5.3	—	4.5
Mean	5.9	5.3	5.0

Table 2. Reaction of MDU4 (ACM16) to low temperature.

Variety	Reaction ^a			
	1985-86	1986-87	1987-88	Mean
ACM16(MDU4)	6.6	7.2	9.6	7.8
MDU2	12.4	11.8	14.1	12.7
IR20	16.4	19.5	15.7	13.7

^aBased on % chaffy grain.

MDU2 in low-temperature areas.

MDU4 is resistant to leaf blast, neck infection, sheath rot, and brown leaf spot under field and artificial conditions. It shows moderate resistance to gall midge and brown planthopper. □

Xiangwanxian 2, an excellent grain quality rice variety derived from an IR line

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Xiangwanxian 2, a short-duration, late rice variety derived from IR19274-26-2-3-1-2 (IR2071/IR2153//IR36) introduced from IRRI, was released Mar 1991 in Hunan. Average yield at 15 locations of the regional provincial test was 6 t/ha in 1990. It has 1000-grain weight of 21.2 g, with 83.8% seed fertility.

Grain quality is superior to that of most indica varieties in China: milled head rice is 58.2%, translucent endosperm, length/width ratio 3.9, 16.1% amylose content, 6% chalky grain, 0.7% area with chalkiness, alkali spreading value 3, 9.1% protein content. These characterize Xiangwanxian 2 as a low-amylose, high to intermediate gelatinization-temperature type similar to international market rices. Cooked grains of Xiangwanxian 2 are soft and cohesive.

Xiangwanxian 2 is semidwarf (90-99 cm), erect and nonlodging, heavy tillering, with 110-d duration. It is suitable as a late crop in Hunan. □

HKR228, a semidwarf aromatic rice strain for Haryana, India

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HKR228 (IET10367) is a semidwarf aromatic rice derived from Sona/Basmati 370. In wet season varietal trials 1985-90, HKR228 yielded 50% more than local check Basmati 370 (Table 1).

HKR228 has 143-d duration, 131 grains/panicle, and 1000-grain weight of 19.0 g. Its grain is long and slender with higher hulling and milling recovery than

Table 1. Yields of HKR228 and Basmati 370 in varietal trials at Kaul and Karnal, Haryana, India.

Year	Location	Yield (t/ha)		LSD (0.05)	CV (%)
		HKR228	Basmati 370		
1985	Kaul	4.9	3.5	0.5	6.8
	Karnal	4.7	2.9	1.2	14.8
1986	Kaul	5.2	3.0	0.3	4.0
	Karnal	5.5	4.8	0.7	6.4
1987	Kaul	6.1	4.3	0.8	6.8
1988	Kaul	4.8	3.5	0.7	8.0
1989	Kaul	5.1	3.6	0.2	2.87
	Karnal	5.5	3.4	0.4	4.02
1990	Kaul	2.8	1.1	0.1	3.20
	Karnal	4.9	2.8	0.6	7.57
Mean		4.95	3.29		

that of Basmati 370. Kernel elongation after cooking is 1.76, with 25.41% amylose content.

HKR228 is resistant to blast, stem rot, and whitebacked planthopper (Table 2).

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed

Neeraja, a high-yielding rice variety for poorly drained rainfed fields in Kerala

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In Kerala, rainfed rice is cultivated on 320,000 ha during the wet season (Apr-May to Sep-Oct). Flooding is a major problem during early crop growth.

We screened 500 entries under poorly drained conditions. After transplanting, the experimental field was flooded to 50 cm for 2 wk.

Promising cultivars were tested for yield at Pattambi and in farmers' fields.

Bangladesh line BR51315-4 was most promising, and has been released as Neeraja (Ptb 47).

Neeraja is semitall (110-120 cm), nonlodging, with 140-d duration (see table). Its grain is white and slender. Yields are 4-5 t/ha under average management (40-9-17 kg NPK/ha). Straw yields

Performance of Neeraja in station and adaptive trials.

Culture or variety	Parentage	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./plant)	Duration (d)		Grain yield (tha)		Mean grain yield (t/ha) from adaptive trials
				Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop	
Neeraja (BR51-315-4)	IR20/Pankaj	115	8	140	55	3.9	1.6	4.9
BR52-96-3	IR20/IR5	108	7	145	55	3.5	1.4	4.4
Ptb 1	Local check	137	7	140	55	1.5	—	2.7
LSD (0.05)						0.7		

Table 2. Characteristics of HKR228 and Basmati 370.

Character	HKR228	Basmati 370
Days to maturity	143	144
Plant height (cm)	116	144
Panicles (no./m ²)	251	269
Grains (no./m ²)	131	89
1 000-grain weight (g)	19.0	21.5
Brown rice (%)	77.8	73.3
Milled rice (%)	72.5	65.0
Kernel length (mm)	7.06	6.70
Kernel breadth (mm)	1.58	1.62
L/B ratio	4.47	4.13
Kernel length after cooking (mm)	12.43	13.54
Kernel elongation ratio	1.76	2.02
Alkali value	6.50	5.05
Amylose content (R)	25.41	19.84
Grain type	Long slender	Long slender
Leaf blast resistance (0-9 scale)	3.0	7.0
Stem rot resistance (0-5 scale)	2.25	2.25
Bacterial leaf blight resistance (0-9 scale)	8.0	9.0
Whitebacked planthopper resistance (0-9 scale)	1.0	0.0

are 8-10 t/ha. Ratoon yields average 1.5 t/ha within 50-55 d. It is moderately resistant to blast and sheath blight.

Neeraja is recommended for poorly drained fields and double-cropped wetlands. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology

Response of blue-green algae (BGA) in wetland rice culture in Himachal Pradesh, India

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We studied during wet season 1990 the effect on rice of BGA inoculation with different levels of applied N. Experimental soil was sandy loam, with pH 7.2, medium organic C (0.60%) and available N (110 kg/ha), and low available P (3.5 kg/ha).

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications; plot size was 5 × 4.75 m.

Thirty-day-old seedlings of IR579 were transplanted 7 Jul 1990. Dry soil-based BGA inoculum was broadcast 10 d after transplanting. The crop was harvested 10 Oct.

A mother culture of BGA procured from the National Facility for Blue-Green Algae Collections, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, at New Delhi was multiplied in the field during June. Ten